

BIOMIMETIC BIOMATERIALS: FUNCTIONING PRINCIPLES, KEY PROPERTIES AND PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

By delivering biomimetic biomaterials it is expected to considerably accelerate implant biointegration, as a result of an increased biorecognition. Biomimetic biomaterials match the natural properties of the tissue and provide multi-functionality, which in turn reduces the gap between the natural material and the synthetic product, thus promoting an optimum ‘symbioses’ between them. Functioning principles of biomimetic materials refer to their overall properties and performance, but can be classified in some main categories: (a) Chemical compatibility through bioactivity; (b) Structural and mechanical performance similar to the natural tissue to be replaced; (c) Texture that will allow the transport of bioactive principles or an incorporated drug-delivery system and (d) Gradient properties or surface functionalization to assure smooth interphases variation of properties from tissue to biomaterial and vice versa. In each of these categories, the key properties are dependent on the replaced tissue. For instance, replacing bone tissue requires a material with appropriate compression modulus - the focus is on the mechanical performance. Synthetic skin also requires appropriate mechanical adjustment but the key property is the elasticity modulus. Biomaterials for synthetic vessels require appropriate surface to eliminate the risk of thrombosis. Further on, the biomaterials that replace parts of a damaged brain must be accordingly built to perform in a humid environment full of electrolytes. Generally, body microenvironment consist in: (1) humidity due to the existence of the body fluids, which influence the radical processes taking place in a biomaterial, changing pathways and reaction kinetics [1], (2) a physiological condition with comparable ranges of load or pressure, viscosity and sliding speed produces friction and complex tribologic phenomena, depending on the tissue location, [2], (3) low intensity electricity generated by the human body through biological electric field and current electrical potentials ranging between 10 and 60 mV at various locations [3], (4) vibrations produced by cyclic loading of the tissues that have elastic properties [4], and (5) complex mechanical loading especially in the case of the musculoskeletal system.

To function in such a complex environment, biomimetic biomaterials have to be personalized with respect to the implant type and situs. They are usually produced by bottom-up techniques to have all the desired properties and functions. An accurate design of what is targeted and good multidisciplinary knowledge combining biology, medicine, materials science, and engineering are demanded. There are several challenges, for example in the case of natural derma, which is an extremely complex tissue. A representative scheme may be seen in Fig.1. The natural skin is made of five up to seven layers that could be synthetically reproduced through a multi-layered composite material. Each layer has a different structure, biochemistry, and function. Its most well-known functions are the self-healing, the thermoregulation and the protection. While the self-healing has been already copied and applied in

polymers engineering and the the protection mechanism has also been applied in synthetic systems, the thermoregulation process is much too complicated to be reproduced in the lab. This is not the only limitation; in the process of construction of a biomimetic synthetic tissue that could mimic the natural derma, the most challenging issue is related to how to join the many layers together without introducing discontinuities between them [5]. The perspectives in this direction are associated to spraying technologies of biocompatible adhesive that could ensure appropriate adhesion and almost zero thickness of the interphase. However, it has to be also considered that the multi-layered composite has to perform in a humid, salty environment at 37⁰ C.

FIGURE 1 Schematic representation of the composition of the natural derma

Finally, some main steps are proposed for an effective process of design, manufacturing and testing of a biomimetic biomaterial: (1) Selection of the application; (2) Market investigation; (3) Scientific investigation – selection of advanced technologies and materials; (4) Preliminary theoretical and experimental studies to select the materials and technologies with higher perspectives; (5) Preparation of experimental protocols; (6) Preparation of experimental setup; (7) Running experimental cycle and (8) Final evaluation and assessment. Comparing to the elaboration process of classic biomaterials, the one related to biomimetic materials presents multiple challenges, new solutions, a highly multidisciplinary approach and unpredicted risks.

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References

1. Dąbrowska-Gralak, M.; Sadło, J.; Głuszewski, W.; Łyczko, K.; Przybytniak, G.; Lewandowska, H. The combined effect of humidity and electron beam irradiation on collagen type I - implications for collagen-based devices, *Materials Today Communications* 2022, 31, 103255.
2. Xi Y. PhD Thesis, Tribological properties of micro/nano-textured surfaces under physiological conditions, University of Groningen 2022, <https://doi.org/10.33612/diss.253871011>.
3. Rouabhia, M.; Park, H.; Meng, S.; Derbali, H.; Zhang, Z. Electrical stimulation promotes wound healing by enhancing dermal fibroblast activity and promoting myofibroblast transdifferentiation, *PLoS One* 2013, 19, 8(8):e71660.
4. Fatemi, M.; Manduca, A.; Greenleaf, J. F. Imaging elastic properties of biological tissues by low-frequency harmonic vibration, *Proceedings of the IEEE* 2003, 91(10), 1503-1519.
5. Portan, D.V.; Ntoulas, C.; Mantzouranis, G.; Fortis, A.P.; Deligianni, D.D.; Polyzos, D.; Kostopoulos. Gradient 3D printed PLA scaffolds on biomedical titanium: mechanical evaluation and biocompatibility, *Polymers* 2021, 13, 682.